

Sensitive extractive spectrophotometric determination of iron(III) with pyridoxal-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone

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A selective and sensitive method is described for the extractive spectrophotometric determination of iron(III), employing pyridoxal-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (PPT) and *n*-butanol as spectrophotometric reagent and extracting solvent, respectively. The extraction behaviour of the complex of iron(III) with the reagent in the pH range 2.5–6.5 and the effects of various metal ions on the extraction are critically studied. Beer's law is valid between 0.5 and 6.0 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The molar absorptivity is $2.3 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Sandell's sensitivity index is 2.428 ng ml^{-1} at 420 nm. The reliability of the method is assured by analysing some standard alloy and pharmaceutical samples.

The existing spectrophotometric methods for the determination of iron(III)¹⁻⁹ generally exhibit moderate sensitivity and the complexes have lower molar absorptivities. The present reagent, pyridoxal-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone offers greater advantages as to its synthesis and instantaneous colour development with iron. The method was applied for the estimation of iron in some standard alloys and pharmaceutical samples.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectrum of Fe^{III}-PPT complex showed λ_{max} at 420 nm where the reagent blank showed negligible absorbance. Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration range 0.5–6.0 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The molar absorptivity was found to be $2.3 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in Ringbom's¹⁰ optimum working range, and Sandell's¹¹ sensitivity index 2.428 ng ml^{-1} of iron.

The precision and accuracy of the method were studied by analysing a series of solutions containing known amounts of iron(III). The standard deviation of the method for the concentration range 0.5–1.5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Fe^{III} was found to be in the range 0.0029–0.0057 and the range of relative standard deviation was 0.58–0.38. The developed colour was found to be stable for 36 h. Constant absorbance was obtained in the pH range 5.0–6.0. Hence, further studies were carried out at pH 5.5. The reagent concentration appropriate for qualitative work was evaluated by plotting a saturation curve. The Fe^{III} concentration was kept constant, while that of PPT was varied between 0.89×10^{-3} and $8.95 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. For a 1 : 6 Fe-PPT molar ratio, complete development of the complex was achieved and remained unaltered for higher proportions.

The effect of various solvents such as chloroform, toluene, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, amyl acetate, ethyl acetate and *n*-butanol, on the extraction of iron(III) with PPT was studied, and *n*-butanol was found to be most suitable. The stoichiometric composition of the complex as determined by Job's method of continuous variation was found to be 1 : 2, which was further confirmed by mole-ratio and slope-ratio methods.

In order to assess possible analytical applications of the method, the effects of diverse ions were studied by adding known amount of the ion to a solution containing 2.5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of iron(III). The tolerance limit was set at the amount required to cause $\pm 1\%$ error in iron recovery. There was no interference due to the presence Li^I, Na^I, K^I, Ca^{II}, Mg^{II}, V^V, Mn^{II}, Ti^{III}, Mo^{VI}, Ag^I, Bi^{III}, Sb^{III}, W^{VI}, chloride, bromide, thiourea, nitrate, acetate, citrate and oxalate upto 2500 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Interference due to Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pd^{II} was suppressed by using oxalate, and Ni^{II} interference was suppressed by using thiourea as masking agents.

The proposed method was compared with other spectrophotometric methods (Table 1) and found to be more sensitive and selective. It offers advantages like reliability and reproducibility in addition to its simplicity, instant colour development and less interference. The results are in good agreement with those obtained by direct AAS method. A relative standard deviation about 0.5% for sample analysis underlines the versatility of the proposed method.

Application : The proposed method was applied to determine iron in alloy (Polymetallic nodules no.2388) and cast iron (standard sample no.73) samples (obtained from

National Metallurgical Laboratory, Jamshedpur, India) and also liquid formulation pharmaceutical samples. The relative standard deviation values were found to be 0.35 and 0.05%, respectively, for Fe^{III} in polymetallic nodules and cast iron samples, while that in liquid formulation pharmaceutical sample such as ferrochelat drops, dexorange plus, incremin syrup and ferrochelat syrup were found to be 0.54, 0.32, 0.43 and 0.52, respectively.

Table 1. Comparison of the present method with other reported methods

Sl. no.	Reagent	pH	λ_{\max} nm	Mol. absorp. (ϵ) $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1} \times 10^4$	Sandell's sensitivity $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$
1.	Biacetylmonoxime thiosemicarbazone ^a	5.3	410	1.45	0.0038
2.	Dipyridylglyoxal-dithiosemicarbazone ^b	5.0–10.0	610	0.71	0.0079
3.	2-(3'-Sulfobenzoyl)-pyridine thiosemicarbazone ^c	4.0–8.8	380	1.24	0.0045
4.	Phenanthroquinonemono-thiosemicarbazone ^d	8.9–9.9	510	0.80	0.0069
5.	Salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone ^e	4.5–5.5	370	1.20	0.0046
6.	Bipyridylglyoxalbis(4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone) ^f	4.7	415	0.79	0.0070
7.	3-Methoxysalicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone ^g	2.0–5.1	590	0.50	0.0112
8.	2-Chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone ^h	6.0	418	0.35	0.0160
9.	2-Methylindole-3-carboxyaldehyde-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone ⁱ	4.0	580	0.42	0.0210
10.	Present method	5.5	420	2.30	0.0024

^aRef. 1. ^bRef. 2. ^cRef. 3. ^dRef. 4. ^eRef. 5. ^fRef. 6. ^gRef. 7. ^hRef. 8. ⁱRef. 9.

Experimental

A Shimadzu 240 UV-VIS spectrophotometer with 1.0 cm quartz cells, a Perkin-Elmer 2380 atomic absorption spectrometer and an Elico LI-120 pH meter were used.

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade and solvents were double-distilled before use. Double-distilled deionised water was used throughout.

A stock solution of iron(III) was prepared by dissolving $\text{NH}_4\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (8.643 g) in double-distilled deionised water (1 dm³) containing sulfuric acid (5 ml) and the solution was standardised volumetrically¹². The ligand pyridoxal-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (PPT) was prepared as per the reported method¹³. A 0.5% solution of PPT was prepared using 40% aqueous dimethylformamide solution. HCl-KCl (pH 1.0–2.6), sodium formate-formic acid (pH 2.6–3.4) and sodium acetate-acetic acid (pH 3.4–6.5) buffer solutions were prepared.

Procedure : To an aliquot of a working standard solution containing 12.5–150 μg iron(III) were added pH 5.5 buffer (3 ml) and 0.5% reagent solution (1 ml). The mixture was shaken with *n*-butanol (2 \times 5 ml) for 1 min and allowed to stand for a few minutes. The organic phase was separated and made upto 25 ml with *n*-butanol and its absorbance was measured at 420 nm against the reagent blank.

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